

ENTREPRENEURIAL ENDEAVORS IN THE ROMANIAN MOUNTAINS: INDUSTRY, CONSTRUCTION, AND SERVICES

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Abstract

The document outlines the entrepreneurial landscape in the Romanian mountains, focusing on the economic sectors of industry, construction, and services. It highlights a crucial turning point in the upward trajectory of mountainous Romania, emphasizing the prominence of the secondary economic sector in the initial phase (2000-2007) and the subsequent dominance of the tertiary/quaternary sectors in the latter part (2008-2018), at the expense of the primary economic sector. Notably, services, particularly those related to summer sales and entertainment, thrive on increased capital inflow during the summer season, driven by the return of emigrants to Romania. The elevated fluctuation in the active enterprise population signifies the pronounced volatility of the mountain economy in Romania. During the latter part of 2008-2018, the economy diversified its

development, relying on additional resources such as information and communication technology (ICT) and food production.

Keywords: mountain entrepreneurship, economic sectors, mountain statistic

Production does not represent much of the industry and services in mountainous Romania, the regional strategy must be based on facilities for the production sectors. In this context, agriculture should not be neglected and agricultural products should be processed locally for the secondary, tertiary and quaternary sectors. Processed products must be distributed at higher prices than primary products, thus adding value to primary production.

The statistics for Industry, constructions and services, except for the insurance activities of the companies (figure 1 - panels a-az), present for each indicator ascending values for average and median, the other statistical indicators having antagonistic fluctuations sometimes (repeated repetitively at each indicator), as follows:

I1 - Average of 226349.9, Error Std. average 13997.8, Median 246416.0, Deviation Std. 46425.5, Skewness -0.9, Kurtosis -0.8, Variation 130479.0, Minimum 144988.0, Maximum 275467.0, Percentile 50 Value 246416.0; I2

- 27335.5, 3339.0, 27931.0, 11074.3, 1.3, 3.9, 43287.0, 11498.0, 54785.0,
27931.0;

I3 - 24347.6, 2998.4, 21223.0, 8995.2, 0.9, -0.5, 25258.0, 14128.0, 39386.0,
21223.0;

I4 - 16094.4, 1111.2, 15179.0, 3685.4, 2.1, 5.4, 12744.0, 13181.0, 25925.0,
15179.0;

I5 - 543.3, 83.8, 433.0, 277.9, 2.1, 4.7, 1014.0, 251.0, 1265.0, 433.0;

I6 - 1237614.3, 25923.3, 1235524.0, 85977.8, -0.7, 0.2, 277991.0,
1065478.0, 1343469.0, 1235524.0;

I7 - 1123610.9, 17809.7, 1096497.0, 59068.2, 0.9, 0.8, 214040.0,
1035313.0, 1249353.0, 1096497.0;

I8 - 50229.1, 3907.9, 48456.0, 12960.9, 1.6, 4.4, 51147.0, 31967.0, 83114.0,
48456.0;

I9 - 33040.1, 1552.5, 32659.0, 5149.1, 0.7, 0.4, 17498.0, 25891.0, 43389.0,
32659.0;

I10 - 36132.2, 2920.1, 34212.0, 8760.2, 0.6, -1.5, 23072.0, 26850.0,
49922.0, 34212.0;

I11 - 19691.1, 2969.1, 16786.0, 8907.3, 1.4, 1.6, 26260.0, 12509.0, 38769.0,
16786.0;

I12 - 53431.8, 2999.4, 50805.0, 9947.8, 1.4, 1.4, 33207.0, 41409.0, 74616.0,
50805.0;

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I13 - 34240.0, 1443.9, 33703.0, 4788.9, 0.9, 0.4, 15262.0, 28577.0, 43839.0, 33703.0;

I14 - 6.2, 5.5, 2.1, 17.5, 2.7, 8.0, 64.1, -10.0, 54.1, 2.1;

I15 - 23.4, 2.4, 19.9, 7.1, 1.3, 1.2, 21.3, 16.9, 38.2, 19.9;

I16 - 11.9, 1.2, 11.3, 3.9, 2.1, 5.6, 14.3, 7.9, 22.2, 11.3;

I17 - 11.0, 1.5, 8.5, 4.6, 0.7, -1.5, 12.1, 5.8, 18.0, 8.5;

I18 - 72.2, 9.7, 62.5, 27.3, 1.1, -0.4, 67.8, 47.3, 115.1, 62.5;

I19 - 7.3, 0.5, 6.8, 1.7, 0.4, -1.3, 4.7, 5.2, 10.0, 6.8;

I20 - 4.1, 0.3, 3.9, 1.0, 2.0, 5.4, 3.9, 2.8, 6.8, 3.9;

I21 - 2.0, 0.1, 1.8, 0.5, 1.9, 4.5, 1.7, 1.5, 3.3, 1.8;

I22 - 68.0, 3.8, 65.8, 12.7, -0.3, 0.5, 45.0, 42.3, 87.3, 65.8;

I23 - 2.9, 0.3, 2.6, 0.8, 0.9, -0.8, 2.3, 2.1, 4.4, 2.6;

I24 - 1.6, 0.1, 1.4, 0.4, 0.7, -0.9, 1.0, 1.2, 2.1, 1.4;

I25 - 55.4, 3.1, 54.1, 10.2, 1.5, 3.3, 38.3, 42.2, 80.6, 54.1;

I26 - 4.3, 0.2, 4.1, 0.8, 0.7, -0.3, 2.5, 3.4, 5.8, 4.1;

I27 - 2.4, 0.1, 2.5, 0.4, -1.9, 4.7, 1.4, 1.5, 2.9, 2.5.

The values presented show that the secondary, tertiary and quaternary sectors have a good development in Romania for indicators I1-2, I4-5, I7-16, I20-21 and I25. Indicators I3, I6, I17-19, I22-24 and I26-27 also show negative values, the general picture showing a good and problematic general mountain entrepreneurial situation for the employment rate, as well as for

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the survival rate of enterprises after three years from establishment. This reflects the employment rate and survival rate of enterprises in the mountain area the general situation in Romania, which has been steadily declining in recent years. According to the National Institute of Statistics in 2020 (trend valid for the last four years), the employment rate of the working age population (15-64 years) was 65.6%, down from the previous year by 0, 2 percentage points. In 2020, the employment rate * of the population aged 20-64 was 70.8%, with 0.8 percentage points above the national target of 70% set in the context of the Europe 2020 Strategy. In 2020 the active population of Romania was 8973 thousand people, of which 8521 thousand were employed and 452 thousand were unemployed” (INS, 2021a).

The same trend is found in the disbanded enterprises, in 2019 “the one-year survival rate of enterprises being over 60%. The proportion of those who have definitively ceased their activity is 4.8%, decreasing by 2.4 percentage points compared to the previous year, and the share of enterprises still inactive one year after the establishment is around 29.0%” (INS, 2021b).

Businesses within active enterprises in the secondary, tertiary and quaternary sectors (except the agriculture sector) can represent Romania's development engine. The multitude of active enterprises, but especially the quality and the added value they give to the local economy leads to the increase of the living standard and the well-being of the population. In this

sense, governmental actions are required, but especially local, in order to develop entrepreneurship. A considerable potential is represented by the mountain area, where the primary products have a high quality value. The local and central measures developed must take into account some of the results of this study.

Panels a – I1, b – I2, c – I3, d – I4, e – I5, f – I6, g – I7, h – I8, i – I9

Panels j – I10, k – I11, l – I12, m – I13, n – I14, o – I15, p – I16, q – I17, r – I18

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Panels s – I19, t – I20, u – I21, v – I22, w – I23, x – I24, y – I25, z – I26, az – I27

Figure 1 Histograms for secondary, tertiary and quaternary sectors for the indicators I1-I27 (2008-2018)

Source: Author according to Eurostat

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The central trend of the secondary, tertiary and quaternary sectors of the economy in the analyzed period shows that the population of active enterprises in mountainous Romania increased considerably from 2008 to 2018. The statistics related to this indicator show a high degree of non-variability, which means that the results they show a large deviation and are positive. The corresponding symmetrical distributions lead to the idea that the business environment begins to stabilize considerably in the analyzed period. Kurtosis with a low standard error is a congestion in some industries, ICT being specific to Romania.

Even though agriculture is still the most important part of the economy, industry and services have grown considerably in volume, which positively influences the number of enterprises in the population.

Indicators for which the study is performed:

- Active business population - number (I1)
- Newly established businesses - number (I2)
- Abolition of businesses in t - number (I3)
- Newly established enterprises in t-3 that have survived to t - number (I4)

- Enterprises with high employment growth (increase of 10% or more) - number (I5)
- Persons employed in enterprises active in t - number (I6)
- Employed in enterprises active in t - number (I7)
- Persons engaged in business established in t - number (I8)
- Employees in businesses established in t - number (I9)
- Persons engaged in business abolished in t - number (I10)
- Employees in businesses dissolved in t - number (I11)
- Persons employed in enterprises newly established in t-3 who have survived to t - number (I12)
- Persons employed in the year of establishment in enterprises newly established in t-3 who have survived to t - number (I13)
- Net business growth - percentage (I14)
- Net business situation: establishment rate + dissolution rate - percentage (I15)
- Establishment rate: number of enterprises established in the reference period (t) divided by the number of enterprises active in t - percentage (I16)
- Dissolution rate: number of enterprises disbanded in the reference period (t) divided by the number of enterprises active in t - percentage (I17)

- 3-year survival rate: number of enterprises in the reference period (t) newly established in t-3 that survived to t divided by the number of enterprises established in t-3 - percentage (I18)
- Share of enterprises aged 3 years in the business population - percentage (I19)
- Employment rate of start-ups: number of persons employed in the reference period (t) among start-ups in t, divided by the number of persons employed in t in the total number of active enterprises - percentage (I20)
- Average size of start-ups: number of persons employed in the reference period (t) among start-ups in t, divided by the number of start-ups in t (I21)
- Rate of new employees paid in enterprises: number of employees in the reference period (t) of newly established enterprises in t, divided by the number of persons employed in t in enterprises newly established in t - percentage (I22)
- Employment rate in disbanded enterprises: number of persons employed in the reference period (t) within the disbanded enterprises divided by the number of persons employed in t in enterprises active in t - percentage (I23)
- Enterprise growth rate of three years: number of persons employed in the reference period (t) in newly established enterprises in t-3, which survived to t, divided by the number of persons employed in t -3 by the same companies, a percentage growth rate - percentage (I24)

- Employment rate of enterprises older than 3 years: number of persons employed in newly established enterprises in t-3 who survived in t, divided by the number of persons employed in active enterprises - percentage (I25)
- Share of high-growth enterprises in employment: number of high-growth enterprises divided by the number of active enterprises with at least 10 employees - percentage (I26)
- Share of enterprises with measured increased growth in employment: number of enterprises with increased growth divided by the number of active enterprises with at least 10 employees - percentage (I27).

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